

Name: _____

Here is the final task, just to see how much knowledge you already have about computing science now that you've almost completed the course. Your answers to this task will **not** count for your final score. Nevertheless, let's see how far you get. Good luck!

PART 1

statement	i <= 6	a	b	i
initialization		1	2	1
test	true			
loop				

What will be the output (printed in the console using *print*) of the algorithm specified by the flowchart above?

PART 2

What will be the output (printed in the console using `System.out.println`) of the algorithm specified by the java code to the right?

Output:

```

int m = 1;
int n = 1;
int i = 10;
while ( i > 4 ) {
    int temp = m + n;
    System.out.println( temp );
    m = n;
    n = temp;
    i--;
}
    
```

PART 3:

An algorithm called `layTrailOfEggs` makes Dodo leave a trail of eggs behind her when she walks. The figures below show the initial situation just before calling `layTrailOfEggs(5)` and just after this call.

Define a method `void int laySquare(int size)` with which Dodo produces a square of eggs. For example, starting with Dodo in the same location as above, `laySquare(6)` should result in the picture on the right. You are free to choose whether you want to use a flowchart to specify your algorithm or to code it directly in Java. Tip: make use of `layTrailOfEggs`.

PART 4:

Specify a **generic** algorithm in **Java code** that produces the spiral pattern on the right (generic means it must work for any world size).

You may **assume** that there is a class constant `WORLD_WIDTH`, and the world's height is equal to the world's width. You may also assume that Dodo's initial location is the upper left corner and is facing East.

Tip: use `layTrailOfEggs` and `turnRight`.

PART 5:

Specify a **generic** algorithm using a flowchart that produces the “squares-in-squares” pattern shown here (generic means it must work for any world size).

You may **assume** that there is a class constant `WORLD_WIDTH`, and the world’s height is equal to the world’s width. You may also assume that Dodo’s initial location is the upper left corner and is facing East.

Tip: use `laySquare`, `move`, `turnRight` and `turnLeft`.

A large empty rectangular box intended for the student to draw a flowchart.